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TOURISM IN RAJASTHAN: A HISTORICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Rajasthan is known for its palaces, it is claimed as the best place for tourism related to palaces. Following are some of the major palaces in Rajasthan.

- Umaid Bhawan Palace: It is the largest Royal Palace in Rajasthan and considered as one of the largest private residences in the world.
- Lake Palace: It is now a luxury hotel located in Pichola Lake, Udaipur.
- Hawa Mahal: It is known as "Palace of Wind" or "Palace of Breeze" because there are more than 950 windows in the palace.
- Rambagh Palace: Formerly a Royal Palace now converted into a Heritage Hotel, known as one of the best Heritage Hotels in the world.
- Devi Garh Palace: Formerly a palace now converted into a Heritage Hotel, in 2006, The New York Times named it as one of the leading luxurious hotels in the Indian subcontinent.

INTRODUCTION:

The Historical Rajasthan, The Land of the Kings, battle-scarred forts, palaces of breathtaking grandeur and whimsical charm, riotous colors and even its romantic sense of pride and honor.

The state is diagonally divided into the hilly and rugged south-eastern region and the barren north-western Thar Desert, which extends across the border into Pakistan. There are plenty of historic cities, incredible fortresses awash with legends, and rare gems of impressionistic beauty, such as Udaipur. There are also a number of centers that attract travelers from far and wide, such as Pushkar with its holy lake, and the desert city of Jaisalmer, which resembles a fantasy. Rajasthan is one of India's prime tourist destinations. Nobody leaves here without

Priceless memories.

Rajasthan is one of the most popular tourist destinations in India, for both domestic and international tourists. Rajasthan attracts tourists for its historical forts, palaces, art and culture. Every third foreign tourist visiting India also travels to Rajasthan as it is part of the Golden Triangle for tourists visiting India. Endowed with natural beauty and a great history, Rajasthan has a flourishing tourism industry. The palaces of Jaipur, lakes of Udaipur, and desert forts of Jodhpur, Bikaner & Jaisalmer are among the most preferred destinations of many tourists, Indian and foreign. Tourism accounts for eight percent of the state's domestic product. Many old and neglected palaces and forts have been converted into heritage hotels. Tourism has increased employment in the hospitality sector. The main sweet of this place is ghewar.

POPULAR TOURIST ATTRACTIONS:

- Ajmer - Popular for shrine of Sufi Saikhllnt Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti.
- Barmer - Barmer and surrounding areas offer perfect picture of typical Rajasthani villages.
- Bikaner - Famous for its havelis, palaces and temples.
- Chittorgarh - Popular for its monument and fort
- Bundi - Popular for its forts, palaces and stepwell reservoirs known as *baoris*.
- Jaipur- Known as pink city of India and the capital of Rajasthan, famous for palaces and temples.
- Jaisalmer - Famous for its golden fortress, havelis and some of the oldest Jain Temples and libraries.
- Jhalawar district - Caves like Binnayaga Buddhist caves, Hathiagor Buddhist Caves, Kolvi Caves are popular medieval architecture of India.
- Jodhpur - Fortress-city at the edge of the Thar Desert, famous for its blue homes and architecture.

- Mount Abu - Popular hill station, famous for 11th century Dilwara Jain Temples and natural beauty. Highest peak in the Aravalli Range of Rajasthan, Guru Shikhar is just 15 km from the main town.
- Nathdwara - This town near Udaipur hosts the famous temple of Shrinathji.
- Neemrana - Located in the heart of the 'golden triangle', Neemrana is almost equidistant from the tourist sites of Delhi, Agra and Jaipur.
- Pushkar - It has the first and one of the very few Brahma temples in the world.
- Ranakpur- Large Jain Temple complex with near 1444 pillars and exquisite marble carvings.
- Ranthambore - Situated near Sawai Madhopur. This town has historic Ranthambore Fort and one of the largest and most famous national park of India (Ranthambore National Park).

The largest tiger in Ranthambore National Park

- Sariska Tiger Reserve - Situated in the Alwar district.
- Shekhawati - Located are small towns such as Mandawa and Ramgarh with frescoed havelis between 100 years to 300 years old, and Vedic period Dhosi Hill.

Udaipur - Known as the "Venice of India".

Top 10 Attractions and Places to Visit in Jodhpur

Jodhpur, the second largest city in Rajasthan (albeit pleasingly unspoilt by haphazard development), has a fascinating past. In case you were wondering, yes, it is where jodhpurs got their name from! These unusual pants were designed by the Maharaja of Jodhpur's son, Pratap Singh, and worn by his polo team when visiting the Queen of England in 1897. Jodhpur is famous for its blue buildings, which were originally painted to signify that they were occupied by Brahmins (the highest caste in India). These 10 Jodhpur attractions and places to visit will give you a diverse experience of the city.

1. Mehrangarh Fort

The impregnable Mehrangarh Fort, which rises above the city, is one of the largest forts in India. As impressive as it is, as a well preserved heritage structure, there's so much more to discover inside. One of the highlights is the museum, which houses an outstanding collection of fine and applied arts from the Mughal period of Indian history. It even has the only professional museum shop in India. The Fort's ramparts are lined with antique artillery and offer a panoramic view of the "Blue City". Do allow plenty of time to visit the Fort -- you can spend hours wandering through it. Want a romantic evening dinner? The Chokelao Mahal Terrace restaurant serves traditional Rajasthani cuisine, while the city sparkles below. The Fort is also an evocative setting for music festivals. Don't miss the annual Rajasthan International Folk Festival in October and World Sufi Spirit Festival in February.

2. Jodhpur Flying Fox

Adventure lovers can't pass up the unique opportunity to go zip-lining with Mehrangarh Fort as the backdrop. The circuit has six zip lines and takes around 1.5 hours to complete. Groups of up to 12 people depart at appointed times.

3. Jaswant Thada

This intricately crafted cenotaph (empty commemorative tomb) was built in 1899, in honor of Maharaja Jaswant Singh II. It features white marble lattice screens and whimsical domes. The inside is adorned with portraits of Ranthore rulers. It's a peaceful place to relax and enjoy stunning views of the Fort and city. Many a tired tourist sprawls on the front lawn to recuperate after sightseeing!

4. Rao Jodha Desert Rock Park

The Rao Jodha Desert Rock Park was developed in 2006, with the aim of restoring the natural ecology of a large rocky wasteland area next to the Fort. Neglected for many years, it was overrun by an invasive thorny shrub. After the shrub was eradicated, over 80 native species of rock-loving plants from the Thar desert were grown there. The Park extends across 70 hectares (around 200 acres) of rehabilitated land and has a walking trail. It's interesting to explore at different times of the year, as its foliage changes with the seasons.

5. Clock Tower and Old City Markets

A trip to Jodhpur wouldn't be complete without visiting the bustling Old City (many people choose to stay in it as well, as some of the best budget hotels in Jodhpur are located there and have fabulous Fort views). The Old City's famous landmark, the clock tower, stands at the heart of it -- and it's still working! Next to it, Sadar Market retains a traditional village bazaar feel. It's chaotic and colorful, and sells almost everything (including handicrafts, spices, saris and fabric). If you feel uncomfortable in crowds, you might prefer to take a walking tour rather than explore the market area yourself, as the congestion can be overwhelming.

6. Umaid Bhawan Palace

The magnificent Umaid Bhawan Palace, completed in 1944, was one of the last great palaces to be built in India. The royal family of Jodhpur still occupies a section of it. Most of the remainder has been converted into a luxurious palace hotel and unfortunately, it's off-limits to anyone who's not staying there. If you can't afford \$600+ per night for a room, you can still get a glimpse inside the palace by having an expensive dinner at one of its restaurants or visiting the museum. The museum mostly displays old photos of the Maharaja and his family. There's a vintage watch and car collection as well. If you're into that kind of thing, it's worthwhile going there. Otherwise, you may be disappointed as you'll get to see very little of the palace.

7. Spice Paradise Cooking Classes

Spice Paradise is a spice shop that's run by a kindhearted husband and wife team (their special *masala chai* blend has been refined and perfected over the years, and is highly recommended). They also conduct Indian cooking classes, which are hugely popular with foreigners, in their humble kitchen. Along with delicious recipes, you'll get to meet a lovely family and gain priceless insight into Indian culture. If you don't have a lot of time in Jodhpur, do book in advance as classes are often full.

8. Janta Sweet Home

If you love not just Indian sweets but all kinds of Indian snacks, you'll definitely want to visit the iconic Janta Sweet Home, renowned for making some of the best treats in Jodhpur.

They're fresh and delicious, and the range is huge. Try: the Mawa Kachori, a prestigious dish that originated from Jodhpur.

9. Sambhali Boutique

Sambhali Boutique is the perfect place to pick up some gorgeous, top quality, Jodhpur handicrafts and clothing (both Indian and western style), all made by underprivileged women who are taught and employed by the Sambhali Trust. Items include silk and cotton camels and elephants, block-printed scarves and curtains, and shoulder bags. Custom orders can also be placed. If you're looking for cheap accommodations, the Sambhali Trust operates from a very charming little guesthouse (the Durag Niwas Guest House) that's a hit with backpackers. Long-term stays with all meals provided are possible.

10. Mandore and Mandore Gardens

Mandore was the capital of the Marwar region before Jodhpur was founded but now it's in a sad state of disrepair. There's an old fort, as well as an eclectic collection of temples and cenotaphs, and a small museum, in the Mandore Gardens. It could be a really attractive tourist spot if it was properly maintained. The monuments are in ruins and garbage is often scattered around. It's still worth a visit though, for the amazing architecture and history of a bygone era. The best time to go is during the week, when it's quietest. If you love monkeys, you'll find plenty there!

Rajasthan are:

Mehrangarh Fort:

The most magnificent fort in Jodhpur is the Mehrangarh Fort. It is situated on a 150m high hill. Rao Jodha, the then chief of Rathore clan, constructed it in 1459. There are a number of attractions within the fort like several palaces, galleries, a Museum, temples and so on.

Umaid Bhavan Palace:

One of the fascinating palaces of Jodhpur is the Umaid Bhavan palace. Maharaja Umaid Singh constructed it in 20th century. A part of the palace has now been converted into a hotel and a museum.

Jaswant Thada:

Jaswant Thada lies to the left of the Mehrangarh fort complex. It is a royal cenotaph made up of white marble. It was built to commemorate Maharaja Jaswant Singh. Some rare portraits of the former rulers of Jodhpur are also displayed here. Along with Jodhpur also explore Jaipur, Pushkar, Ranakpur and Udaipur through Rajasthan is the state in the West India. It is also known as "the land of kings" and "the land of colours". It houses the Great Indian desert(Thar Desert). Jaipur is the capital city of the state, also known as Pink city. The famous cities are Jaipur, Ajmer, Chittorgarh, Jodhpur, Udaipur, Kota, Jaisalmer etc.

Rajasthan is famous for the majestic forts, intricately carved temples and decorated havelis. Jantar Mantar, Chittorgarh Fort, Lake Palace, City Palaces, Jaisalmer Havelis are part of the true architectural heritage of India. Dilwara Temples of Mount Abu, Ranakpur Temple dedicated to Lord Adinath near Udaipur, Jain temples in the fort complexes of Chittorgarh, Jaisalmer and Kumbhalgarh, Lodurva Jain temples, Bhandasar Temple of Bikaner are some of the best examples. There are fairs with snake charmers, puppeteers, acrobats and folk performers. Camels, of course, play a stellar role in this festival. Keoladeo National Park of Bharatpur, Sariska Tiger Reserve of Alwar, Ranthambore National Park of Sawai Madhopur, and Desert National Park of Jaisalmer are famous wild life attraction in the state.

REFERENCE

1. Krishna, A.G., 1993 "Case study on the effects of tourism on culture and the environment: 2. India; Jaisalmer, Khajuraho and Goa"
3. Honey, Martha and Gilpin, Raymond, Special Report, 2009, "Tourism in the Developing World - Promoting Peace and Reducing Poverty"
4. Market Research Division, Ministry of tourism, GOI, 2009 "Tourism Statistics 2008"
5. *Rajasthan*, by Monique Choy, Sarina Singh. Lonely Planet, 2002.
6. *In Rajasthan*, by Royina Grewal. Lonely Planet Publications, 1997.
7. <http://traveljee.com/india/top-10-beautiful-royal-palaces-forts-rajasthan/>
8. www.ibef.org

9. www.incredibleindia.org
10. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tourism>
11. <http://www.gdrc.org/uem/eco-tour/envi/index.html>
13. Research journal of arts, management & social sciences
14. International research journal of commerce , arts and science
17. News Paper